

Information Systems in Management Sciences: A Literature Review

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ABSTRACT

In a context marked by accelerated digitalization and the growing complexity of organizational environments, information systems (IS) occupy a strategic position in corporate governance. Their contribution is no longer limited to a technical role, but is part of a dynamic of structural, organizational, and decision-making transformation. However, the academic literature remains fragmented, between technocentric approaches, sociotechnical analyses, and strategic perspectives, making an integrated vision of the role of IS difficult. This article offers a critical and structured review of the main theoretical approaches used in management science to study IS. It is based on a three-step analytical approach: (1) a rereading of the conceptual and historical foundations of the field; (2) a structuring of research according to three dominant visions: "adoption," "appropriation," and "organizational impact"; (3) an analysis of strategic alignment models, notably Management of Information Technology Model and Strategic Alignment Model. The results highlight the paradigmatic evolution of the field towards more integrative approaches and the need to articulate theoretical frameworks and empirical contexts. The article argues in favor of a methodological hybridization, combining theoretical depth and field anchoring, to fully understand the transformative potential of IS. It thus opens up avenues of research focused on the dynamics of alignment, appropriation processes and tensions between technical devices and organizational structures.

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I. INTRODUCTION

In an organizational environment profoundly transformed by the acceleration of technological change, the increasing digitalization of business processes, and the emergence of new data-driven economic models, the integration of information systems (IS) is emerging as a major strategic lever for companies. Information systems are no longer limited to their technical or instrumental dimensions; they play a central role in value creation, structuring decision-making processes, organizational governance, and implementing innovation strategies (Gofwan, 2022). In this context, their alignment with the company's overall strategy is becoming a crucial issue, both conceptually and managerially. It is no longer simply a matter of deploying effective technological tools; it is also a matter of ensuring that they sustainably support strategic directions and integrate seamlessly with existing structures and processes (Chan & Reich, 2007).

Far from being a stable field, information systems research in management science has developed along multidisciplinary lines, at the intersection of computer science, organizational

sociology, strategic management, and innovation theories. Since the pioneering work of Davis in 1967 and the institutionalization of the field with the creation of the journal *Management Information Systems Quarterly* in 1977, information systems have gradually been recognized as a research topic in their own right within management science. The development of this field has been accompanied by an evolution in research paradigms: initially focused on the technical and functional dimensions of information systems, studies have gradually integrated more holistic approaches, taking into account the human, social, political, and cultural dynamics at work in organizations (De Vaujany, 2009).

This growing complexity has fostered the emergence of diverse theoretical frameworks, ranging from the analysis of technological adoption and acceptance to the study of appropriation processes, including strategic evaluation models. It has also sparked significant methodological debates, particularly regarding the need to combine qualitative and quantitative analyses, interpretive and positivist approaches, to grasp the complexity of interactions between information systems and organizational structures.

In this context, this article offers a critical perspective on the major theoretical approaches to information systems in management science, highlighting the tensions, intersections, and complementarities between technological, organizational, and human dimensions. It adopts a three-pronged analytical stance: first, a rereading of the historical and conceptual foundations of information systems research, allowing us to understand the logic of the emergence and structuring of the field; second, a structuring of the approaches based on the dominant visions of "adoption," "appropriation," and "organizational impact," which permeate the literature. Third, an in-depth discussion of strategic alignment models as a point of convergence for the dynamics between information systems and organizations.

The objective is twofold: first, to provide a critical and structured perspective on the evolution of the field of information systems in management science; second, to identify conceptual and analytical levers for considering the integration of information systems at the heart of contemporary organizational dynamics. This paper is part of a theoretical structuring approach prior to future empirical research, aimed at better understanding the conditions for success or failure of the strategic alignment of information systems in changing organizational contexts.

II. HISTORY OF INFORMATION SYSTEMS RESEARCH IN MANAGEMENT SCIENCES

The genesis of research in the field of information systems dates back to the founding of the journal "Management Information Systems Quarterly" (MISQ) in 1977, marked by the first major international conference on information systems, the "International Conference on Information Systems" (ICIS), which took place in 1980 in Philadelphia, Pennsylvania.

An undisputed pioneer of this discipline is "Davis", who established, in 1967, a doctorate in Management Information Systems at the University of "Minnesota". His work focused on crucial aspects such as information systems planning and knowledge management. In addition, the "Journal of Computer Automation and Operational Research" of the "French Association for Economic and Technical Cybernetics" played a significant role by publishing pioneering articles in the field of information systems, particularly under the heading "Information Systems Engineering". This journal, which changed its name in 1998 to become the "Association of Information Sciences and Technologies", now brings together various associations, including the "Association for the Development of Computer Logic", created in 1978 and specializing in the design of information systems with an engineering-based approach (Drain, 2014).

In its early days, information systems research was closely linked to the computer science discipline, sometimes leading to confusion between information systems and computer systems. However, it is important to note that a company's

information system is not limited to its computer system. Early studies were mostly non-empirical, focusing on the technical aspects of information systems development and exploring issues related to decision-making. "Canada" played an active role in the emergence of this field, as evidenced by the doctoral thesis of Raymond in 1984 entitled "An empirical study of the success factors of an information system in the context of SMEs." This thesis examined the validity of information systems analyses developed for large organizations when applied to SMEs, also highlighting the essential contribution of information systems to value creation. However, in the 1960s and 1970s, the deterministic perspective remained predominant, with information technologies perceived as a kind of external imperative to organizational actors (He and al., 2021).

Reix (1992) emphasizes that the field of information systems finds its place within the discipline of management science, thus establishing a significant link between information systems and the organization. He strengthens this connection by establishing information systems management as a specific field, distinct from computer science and information science. This link is essential, as Charreaux and Pitol-Belin (1992) show, because organizations are social systems created by individuals with the aim of satisfying certain needs and achieving objectives through coordinated actions. Thus, all companies, whether private or public, can be considered as organizations integrated into this systemic context (Pearlson and al., 2024).

The 1980s and 1990s were crucial in firmly anchoring the field of "Information Systems" within management sciences and in stabilizing a research agenda. A study conducted by Claver and al. (2000), based on the analysis of articles from major journals such as "Management Information System Quarterly" and "Information & Management" over the period (1981-1997), highlights the diversity of themes addressed in information systems research. This discipline remains relatively young, but the work carried out has contributed to establishing a solid base. Claver and al. (2000) develop a typology of information systems research themes, thus highlighting the richness and diversity of the questions explored in this field.

Table 1: Themes retained in the study by Claver and al. (2000)

Themes
Information Systems Assessment
Development and Implementation
Organizational Impact, Reengineering
Technology Diffusion
Information Systems Security
Decision Support, Expert Systems, Artificial Intelligence
Databases, Data Warehouses

Interorganizational Systems (e-business, EDI)
Collaborative Work, Groupware, Intranet
Strategic IT, Planning
HR Management for IT Professionals
Information Systems Research
Miscellaneous

Desq and al. (2002) suggest a less analytical approach to establishing a typology of information systems research. Their overview identifies thirteen issues grouped around three main themes: strategic management of information systems, development, and control. These themes correspond to the main levels of information systems management, thus applying the general triptych "strategy, development, and control" to the field of information systems. In addition, these researchers propose a classification by application domain, distinguishing five areas: Informational (Data and knowledge management), Functional (Transaction processing and support for operational tasks), Decisional (Decision-making processes and decision support), Relational (Communication processes and communication support), and General (Information System as a whole). Finally, the examination of the publications analyzed by Desq and al. (2002) highlights that evaluation constitutes the dominant issue in the works reviewed, encompassing various themes. This predominance of the question of evaluation can be associated with the questioning of the imputation of the contribution of information and communication technologies to organizational performance.

During this period, the majority of articles focused on the relationship between information and communication technologies (ICT), organization, and performance, in various forms. De Vaujany (2009) revisits Morgan's (1998) seven-image model of the organization, which conceptualizes the organization from seven perspectives: a machine, a living system, a brain, a social system, a culture, a political system, a mental prison, and an instrument of domination. Each image is associated by De Vaujany (2009) with a specific view of the information system. Drawing on Morgan's (1998) sociological view of the organization, this approach enriches the understanding of information systems by integrating them with theories from disciplines such as sociology and, more broadly, the humanities. This offers a diversity of perspectives for exploring the complex dynamics between information and communication technologies, organization, and performance.

These developments in the field of information systems stem from technological advances. During this period, decision support systems were marked by the emergence of expert systems. At the same time, there is a growing trend towards integrating practitioner perspectives into research. The work of Zmud (2000) suggests action research approaches that place greater emphasis on the interpretivist

dimension. Similarly, Akoka and Comyn-Wattiau (2006) particularly highlight the correlation between the technological dimension of information systems and their organizational dimension, thus highlighting the interconnection between these two essential aspects.

Becker and Schmid (2020) point out that although computer science is undoubtedly the founding discipline of information systems, other scientific fields also contribute to its genesis, such as information science, management and organizational theory, sociology of technology, economics, psychology, and philosophy. He concludes that, within the landscape of sciences, information systems sometimes find itself in a delicate position, with sometimes permeable boundaries between management science, social science, and engineering science. Nevertheless, information systems research has managed to establish itself as a distinct branch within management science.

III. DEFINITION OF INFORMATION SYSTEMS

The term "system" originates from the Greek word "systêma" and the verb "systeô," meaning to tie together and intertwine. A system is defined as a set of closely related, interconnected parts, where one or more parts assume a more important character, referred to as the principle of the system. This notion is reminiscent of order, but it encompasses a more precise and complex order, because the parts are linked by relationships of resemblance, homogeneity, and mutual dependence. A system is the arrangement of the different parts of an art or science in a mutually supportive order; the latter being explained by the former. The parts responsible for explaining the others are designated as principles, and the perfection of a system lies in the reduction of these principles to a limited number, or even to a single principle. Thus, a system represents an attempt to explain a set of things in a specific order, and a systematic mind coordinates its knowledge to reduce it to a small number of principles, or even just one (Laudon and Laudon, 2017).

The term "information" derives from the Latin verb "informare," meaning to give form to or form an idea of. It encompasses both the message to be communicated and the signs used to write it, relying on a meaningful code intended for the unique understanding of the recipient. Information is characterized by its form (oral, textual, etc.), its mode of presentation (digital, alphabetical, etc.), its qualities (reliable, objective, confidential, precise, etc.), and its cost. Within an organization, it must meet seven significant criteria: effectiveness, efficiency, confidentiality, integrity, availability, compliance, and reliability. As a fundamental resource for any organization, information is an intangible asset and an immaterial resource to be processed, deciphered, and selected as needed. It constitutes the raw material fueling processes within the organization. Today, information is essential for decision-making and business management. For most organizations, it is the *raison d'être*,

and therefore, a lack of information or poor communication can lead to significant financial losses or even the cessation of the organization's activity (Laudon and Laudon, 2017).

In 2000, "Reix" defined an information system as an organized set of resources including hardware, software, personnel, data, and procedures. These elements are orchestrated to acquire, process, store, and communicate information in various forms (data, text, images, sounds, etc.) within organizations. In 2002, "Reix and Rowe" enriched this definition by describing the information system as a grouping of social actors who memorize and transform representations through information technologies and operating modes. These two perspectives not only define the contours and content of the information system, but also highlight the existence of social interactions between the various actors (Reix and al., 2016).

Kéfi and Kalika (2004) define an information system as a combination of formal processes encompassing the collection, storage, processing, and dissemination of information. These processes, anchored in technological tools, support transactional and decision-making activities, as well as communication processes between organizational actors, whether individuals or groups, within one or more organizations:

- Collection: Information can be internal, produced by the organization itself, or external, arriving from outside. It is important to monitor market developments and select the relevant information for sound decision-making.
- Storage: All collected information must be preserved and, at the same time, organized, accessible, and available over time, hence the need to choose a storage method that guarantees its sustainability.
- Processing: All stored information is intended to be processed and interpreted for the benefit of the organization to derive maximum benefit from it through the resulting decision-making.
- Dissemination: All processed information must therefore be disseminated, made available, and reached its recipient, who must use it in accordance with the decision made.

O'brien and Marakas (2006) put forward a definition of the information system by conceiving it as an entity constituted, on the one hand, by linking and positioning procedures that provide relevant information and allow the execution of management actions, and on the other hand, by the material and human resources necessary to process, store and transfer this information for their concrete exploitation. This perspective highlights the coexistence of individuals, material resources and procedures within an organization. Furthermore, the definition of Nurcam and Rolland (2006) completes this vision by characterizing the information system as an organized set of technological and human resources intended to facilitate the realization of the organization's activities, thus highlighting the crucial role of individuals and technologies in this context.

Based on these definitions, it is possible to observe a close interconnection between technologies and information systems. This correlation stems mainly from the fact that certain technical tools in the field of information technology often provide essential support for the implementation of information systems. Indeed, technology is emerging as a fundamental element promoting the deployment and integration of information systems within the company.

1. IT or ICT

The concept of information technology (IT) encapsulates the convergence of various technical advances, encompassing microelectronics, computer science, telecommunications, software engineering, and systems analysis. This convergence gives rise to a panoply of tools capable of ensuring high performance in recording, storing, analyzing, and transmitting information. Information technology is thus distinguished from other technologies by its ability to manipulate information. In other words, it goes beyond the automation of information processing processes; it also generates the creation of information at levels of volume and processing speed never before achieved (McLoughlin and al., 2000).

In the field of new technologies, a variety of acronyms (NICT, NIT, ICT, ...) emerge, each emphasizing a specific aspect: innovation, information, or communication. The term "information technology" first appeared in American publications in the years 1974-1975. In Anglo-Saxon literature, the keywords associated with articles are (ICT) for "Information and Communication Technology" or (IT) for "Information Technology." According to the work of Bomsel (2007), these technologies took shape in the 1960s, based on three fundamental principles: logic processing, digital technology, and the electrical signal within integrated electronic circuits.

Bomsel (2007) identifies the use of the terms "information technology" or "communication technology" specifically in the context of education in the 1980s. Although the association of the terms "technology" and "information" is long-standing, the more recent emergence of the term "new information and communication technologies" (NICT) is explained by the perception that these technologies do not seem to be able to stabilize and are aging quickly. This concept encompasses products and services resulting from the integration of the four main technologies: computers, electronics, telecommunications, and audio and video.

2. Evolution of information systems architectures

Since the 1970s, networking of equipment has paved the way for data transfer between multiple geographic locations within a single company. The development of networks, with their varied protocols, has facilitated remote file exchange and communications, thus becoming an essential component of information and communication technologies. The evolution of IT architectures can be conceptualized through three distinct phases. The first, called centralized, is

characterized by the existence of a single mandatory route passing through a central point. This configuration, predominant in the 1970s, involves a concentration of hardware and software at a single point, symbolized by a central computer, commonly called a "mainframe." The second phase, called decentralized, which became established in the 1980s-1990s, involves the establishment of at least two centers. This architecture can be illustrated by departmental IT, where each major function of the company has its own server. This approach represents an evolution from centralization, offering greater autonomy to the different departments. Finally, the third phase, known as distributed architecture, marks a break with the previous two. In this model, there is no single center but several different routes to reach a particular node. The node, in this context, represents an element connected to the network, such as a workstation, a server, or even a printer. This architecture, emerging after the 1990s, favors increased flexibility and redundancy of communication paths (Drain., 2014).

Over the decades, the evolution of IT architectures has been marked by significant transformations, responding to the growing needs of organizations and technological advances. In the 1970s, the era of mainframes emerged, enabling the processing of massive volumes of data with key functions such as sorting, processing, and retrieval. The 1980s witnessed several major developments. First, the advent of minicomputers paved the way for the client-server model, characterizing the era of departmental computing. This approach aimed to meet the real-time operational needs of departments, facilitating data access and information sharing (Drain., 2014).

In 1985, the introduction of personal computers brought processing autonomy, marked by autonomous processing power and user-friendly graphical interfaces. The 1990s were marked by the rise of local and enterprise networks, as well as the integration of multimedia. This period favored the sharing of resources and peripherals, and accelerated the validation of standards. In 1995, the emergence of wide-area networks and web technology paved the way for the sharing of collaborative applications, also marking the widespread adoption of the Internet Protocol (IP) for all information (Drain., 2014).

The 2000s were characterized by the adoption of service-oriented architecture (SOA), enabling service interoperability, nomadism, and resource virtualization. In the following decade, cloud computing and the “Bring Your Own Device” (BYOD) philosophy took center stage. These advances facilitated access to private, public, or mixed networks, resource sharing, and introduced on-demand usage and pay-as-you-go models. A clearer distinction between uses and infrastructures also emerged, allowing the use of private mobile devices within organizations. Thus, this timeline demonstrates the continued adaptation of IT

architectures to the evolving needs of businesses (Drain., 2014).

IV. APPROACHES TO INFORMATION SYSTEMS RESEARCH IN MANAGEMENT SCIENCES

We have previously established that computer science is the founding discipline of information systems. However, it is possible to discern three specific visions of this field. The first vision, entitled "focused on adoption, acceptance and appropriation", highlights the contours of technology adoption, the associated processes, as well as the practices implemented within a company. The second vision, "focused on technologies and the organization", focuses more specifically on the relationship between information technologies and organizational structure, with a particular emphasis on performance. Finally, the third vision, "focused on the study of the information system", is manifested through research focusing not only on the in-depth study of the information system but also including the possible modifications and transformations that can be envisaged (Duan and Da Xu, 2024).

These three visions remain interconnected, revolving around two distinct questions: "why" and "how." The "why" question directs investigations toward more descriptive approaches. Conversely, the "how" question guides investigations toward more analytical approaches. We will only present the first two visions, as they are closely linked to management science research.

1. The vision focused on adoption, acceptance and appropriation

The perspective focusing on information system adoption emerges as one of the most explored in the literature. Studies devoted to adoption can be grouped into three distinct thematic categories. First, there is research that approaches adoption from a restrictive perspective, focusing on the systems specifically chosen within the organization. Second, some studies focus on acceptance, giving a prominent place to the actors involved. Finally, a third category of studies explores appropriation, analyzing the "how" of adoption in a broader context. This thematic classification provides a useful structure for understanding the diversity of approaches related to the adoption of information systems.

A. Types of technologies

Hickson and al. (1969), following on from Woodward J.'s research, distinguish between three broad categories of technologies. First, they identify operational technologies, which encompass equipment related to the workflow. Then, they define hardware technologies, which group together the tools used in the workflow. Finally, they address knowledge-based technologies, which correspond to the tools supporting knowledge in the workflow.

Vacher (2002) distinguish two categories of technologies. The first group, consisting of older technologies, focuses on

the automation of processes and procedures. These technologies promote cross-functionality and consistency of operations within the organization. On the other hand, the second group, consisting of more recent technologies linked to the introduction of the Internet, gives rise to the proliferation of new activities, such as e-commerce.

Furthermore, Benghozi (2001) identifies three categories of technologies. The first group of technologies targets information management for each member of the organization. The second group focuses mainly on communication technologies within the organization. Finally, the third group includes technologies essential to the functioning of the organization's internal processes.

Overall, these diverse perspectives demonstrate the ongoing complexity and dynamics of the information technology field within the organizational context. They highlight the constant evolution of these technologies, highlighting the absence of total stability. The developed classification offers a structured view of the multiple natures and functions of technologies within work processes. By examining the varied implications of technologies in organizational practices, this perspective provides a thorough understanding of the changes underway. Indeed, it highlights the evolution of technologies and their specific role in information management, communication, and operational processes within organizations, thus contributing to the dynamic perception of this constantly evolving field.

B. Adoption of a technology

Simon H., winner of the 1978 Nobel Prize in Economics, stands out as one of the pioneers in the field of information systems and decision support. His work critiques neoclassical theory, which attributes extremely strong rationality to individuals. To address this, Simon developed the concepts of "procedural rationality" and "information processing systems" (Reix, 2004). In contrast to neoclassical theory, which assumes that individuals can identify all alternatives, measure the consequences of their actions, and choose the most satisfactory alternative, Simon proposes a model called Intelligence Modeling Choice (IMC). This organizational model of decision-making highlights the importance of process in decision-making, establishing links between humans and decisions as well as organizations and information. It analyzes the relationships between organizations and technologies, thus offering an enriching perspective on decision-making mechanisms (Aldunate and Nussbaum, 2013).

However, although this model offers an illuminating perspective on decision-making mechanisms, it has shortcomings when it comes to dealing with innovative decisions or crisis decisions, especially in times of difficulties within the company. It significantly neglects the role of the negotiation and influence process within the organization in determining decision-making. In addition, the interrelationships between the different actors involved in the decision-making process are rarely addressed. For

example, in the case of an SME working as a subcontractor for a large group, the adoption of the same IT tool for the exchange of electronic data is often imposed by the large group, thus highlighting the dimension of power relations that is not adequately explained in the model (Reix, 2016).

Thomas and Rogers (1998) developed a typology that distinguishes five forms of innovation adoption. According to this classification, innovators are positioned as the first acquirers of the technology, early adopters represent the social leaders promoting diffusion, majorities are the central actors in the propagation of the technology, late adopters make their purchase when the technology reaches maturity, and finally, laggards are the last to adopt the technology. This typology offers a thorough understanding of the different phases of innovation adoption within a technological context.

Burton-Jones and al. (2021) highlights the need to distinguish between technology adoption and appropriation, thus introducing the concept of "guarantee value." According to him, innovation is desired not only for its functional contributions, but also for its symbolic value. He uses the evocative metaphor that technology is a kind of medal on display. In our research, we are situated in this initial phase of adoption, focusing our attention on the acquisition of a technology. Although the literature offers a wealth of information on the factors that can influence technology adoption, it does not always explain in detail the underlying determinants of this adoption.

C. Acceptance of a technology

Davis (1989) introduced the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) in a study commissioned by IBM, focusing on the appropriation and assimilation phase of a technology rather than the adoption phase. The TAM model postulates that user acceptance of a technology depends on two key factors: perceived usefulness and perceived ease of use, thus forming a cost/benefit balance. According to this model, users' perceptions of usefulness and ease of use influence their propensity to adopt information and communication technologies, which, in turn, impacts their intentions to use them (Davis, 1989). The TAM model has been empirically validated numerous times through statistical studies, thus maintaining a prominent position (Venkatesh and al., 2003). Other notable contributions highlight that personal factors such as decision-making style, cognitive style, or even users' attitudes towards a system, exert an influence on the acceptance of a technology (Chaumon, 2016 ; Marikyan and Papagiannidis, 2021).

D. Appropriation of a technology

Rogers and Williams (1983) developed the theory of diffusion of innovation, highlighting the central role of communication in this evolutionary process. This theory finds its place specifically in the technology appropriation phase. To further understand appropriation, Proulx (2002) elaborates a crucial distinction between accessibility, use, and appropriation. Accessibility refers to the availability of a

technology on the market, while actual use involves a user using that technology in a specific task. The final stage of this process is appropriation, marking the moment when the user fully integrates the technology into their daily lives. This progressive perspective emphasizes the importance of moving from mere accessibility to actual use, ultimately culminating in the complete appropriation of the technology (Nguyen and al., 2021).

Although this approach grants a role to actors, it nevertheless stems from a technical perspective. Certainly, actors can compromise the dynamics when technologies are not sufficiently appropriated. However, the extent to which actors are capable of inventing new technologies is little studied. Furthermore, the way in which actors, by appropriating technologies, can innovate new uses is not truly taken into account. This perspective maintains technologies as entities external to actors, leaving aside the creative dimension of the latter in the co-construction of technologies and their uses (Bermeo-Andrade and González-Bañales, 2021).

2. The vision centered on technologies and the organization

The technology-organization perspective, explored in particular by Woodward in 1965 and Markus and Robey in 1988, is dedicated to the in-depth analysis of technological innovations and their impact on the structure of production systems within firms. Also known as the "technical causal" school, this approach has its origins in the sociotechnical school, which, unlike other schools, emerged in Europe rather than the United States. In 1965, Trist and Emery conceptualized this approach by demonstrating that the organization constitutes a sociotechnical system. From this perspective, improving working conditions requires simultaneous action on the social system and technology, thus highlighting the importance of the interactions between these two components for organizational development and effectiveness.

The link between product process innovation and productivity improvement is illustrated by the famous paradox formulated by Solow (1987): "We can see computers everywhere except in productivity statistics." This paradox has stimulated much research, with Mairesse and Sassenou (1991) highlighting the lack of statistics on computer use and investments in information and communication technologies. In response, Brynjolfsson and Hitt (1993) presented the first statistical results on the returns to ICT investments, based on a sample of large US firms. Since then, the number of econometric studies addressing this issue has steadily increased, demonstrating the continued importance of this issue in the research field.

Laudon and Laudon (2017) demonstrate that companies aspire to optimize their returns by combining the use of technical and social systems in a coordinated manner. This approach aims to account for the process of mutual

adaptation within a sociotechnical system. These two perspectives are particularly suited to explaining the challenges encountered when implementing a sophisticated information system that does not meet user expectations. Contrasting with the previous vision, which presents a system "imposed" by the adoption-process approach, we move to a "constructed" model that establishes operating rules (both explicit and implicit) as well as usage standards, imposing a pre-established structure on the different actors. This approach has both a technical and a behavioral dimension, in addition to presenting an integrated capacity for evolution (Laudon and Laudon, 2017).

Pesqueux (2002) highlights the importance of the link between the information system and the organization. Adopting a systemic perspective, this author explains that the information system can be considered as a means at the service of the actors of the organization, thus revealing itself transparent to the contours of the latter. However, he also suggests the possibility that the information system, as an entity, can structure the organization itself. He advocates granting the information system relative autonomy, thus moving away from the idea that it is simply an instrument that can be mobilized at will to orchestrate organizational change. The author emphasizes that this relationship can adopt three distinct postures. The first posture embraces a deterministic approach where the organization emerges as the product of technology, leading some authors to speak of technological contingency, particularly with regard to IT. The second position reverses the role, arguing that the structure of the organization is forged by the intentions of its designers, thus denoting the independence between technology and appropriate means. Finally, the last position rejects the idea of technological or organizational determinism, favoring instead an interaction between these two elements and the social context (Pesqueux, 2002).

From the perspective that emphasizes the interdependencies between the information system and the organization, we can briefly outline two significant models: the diamond model of Leavitt and March (1962) and the model of Bostrom and Heinen (1977). These models, inspired by sociotechnics, establish the organizational structure at the heart of the interrelationships between technology and individuals. They explicitly link the configuration of the organization, the human factor, and technology. By adopting an integrative vision that takes into account both the social and technical dimensions of the information system, Leavitt and March (1962) and Bostrom and Heinen (1977) manage to overcome the limitations of the institutional school. These interrelationships generate organizational transformations. Take, for example, the case where a company opts to implement a secure network such as a "Virtual Private Network" (VPN). The introduction of this new technology induces organizational changes, such as the possibility of working from home. Organizational members can connect without constraints, necessarily leading to organizational

adjustments. This dynamic can also lead to the development of new activities or the elimination of existing ones.

On the other hand, Kalika and al. (2007) with their millefeuille theory, indicate that the development of a communication tool in business management does not generally lead to a substantial reorganization of communication and coordination management processes. This results in a stacking effect of tools, called the "millefeuille effect". This expression reflects the fact that communication means accumulate on top of each other without any real integration or synergy between them.

Management challenges are examined through a dual lens, both social and technical. This implies that any problem within the company must be understood through four categories of key actors: hardware and software suppliers, social actors evolving in the company's environment, available and in-use technical investments, and employees. The company is thus conceptualized as an open system, characterized by a superposition of various architectural layers, including varied hardware and software. As a result, the whole may present a certain coherence, but above all, it acquires a notable complexity. This complexity can become a significant obstacle to the evolution of the information system within the company (Bollinger, 2020).

V. EVALUATION OF INFORMATION SYSTEMS IN MANAGEMENT SCIENCES

Since the institutionalization of the field of "Information Systems Management," evaluation-oriented approaches have been explored. It is crucial to emphasize that the primary objective of an information system is the effective communication of information to stakeholders. This information is essential for the management team to develop, consolidate, and validate its strategy. Consequently, the evaluation of an information system generally leads to adjustments and, more specifically, to modifications or even transformations of the system. The evaluation of an information system cannot be carried out meaningfully without a prior clarification of the organizational strategy. This evaluative approach is thus part of an iterative process aimed at ensuring the optimal alignment of the information system with the organization's strategic objectives (Cronholm and Goldkuhl, 2003).

Generally speaking, the academic corpus on information system evaluation is structured around three distinct approaches (Willcocks, 2013):

The first approach highlights the crucial importance of the information system and its central role in the overall functioning of the organization. This perspective, illustrated by the work of Porter and Millar in 1985, highlights the strategic position of information and communication technologies within the value chain. These technologies have the potential to transform the company's activities and play a crucial role in supporting competitive advantage.

The second approach, often referred to as the resource-based approach, considers technology as one resource among others available to the firm. It emphasizes that firm performance stems from the effective coordination of internal and external resources. However, this approach, while relevant, remains imprecise in its definition of resources in general and fails to comprehensively explain the factors leading to changes in the information system.

Finally, the third approach, known as "strategic alignment," has given rise to several significant models that focus on the optimal synchronization between the company's overall strategy and its information system, thus providing an integrated perspective for evaluating and guiding the development of the information system in accordance with the organization's strategic objectives (Willcocks, 2013).

1. Management of Information Technology Model

Research on information technology-induced strategic change draws primarily on concepts borrowed from theories of strategic management, information management, industrial engineering, and organizational behavior. A fundamental approach is the Management of Information Technology (MIT) model formulated by Morton (1991). According to this model, investments in information systems generate transformations that affect strategy, technology, structure, management processes, and individuals within the organization. The discussion aims to categorize the main research areas under three distinct headings: process reengineering, IT-enabled transformation, and human-centered renewal. This categorization is intended to reflect a comprehensive review of the literature, consistent with the MIT model framework. With this foundation, the discussion explores the main concerns and emerging issues in the literature in this specific area (Morton and al., 2019).

The concept of "process reengineering" originates from industrial engineering and focuses primarily on the "business process" element within the MIT framework (Morton, 1991). This approach aims to optimize processes to increase operational efficiency. The main objective is to introduce process innovations to achieve significant improvements in terms of lead times, quality, and cost reduction. These new methods are often implemented by dedicated project teams, focused on customer needs and supported by advanced IT technologies. Despite the significant progress made in performance, companies sometimes find it difficult to maintain them due to the resulting imbalance with other organizational aspects (Morton and al., 2019).

Similarly, the perspective of "IT-enabled transformation" focuses on the harmonization of information technology with the "strategy" and "structure" aspects within the framework of the MIT model (Morton, 1991). Information technology thus becomes a strategic tool aimed at optimizing resource allocation. This redefinition of resource

allocation and the scope of business activity is profoundly transforming the nature of modern businesses, generating a significant impact on intra- and inter-firm social relations. Faced with these developments, organizations must develop new approaches to establish internal "trust" and foster coherence between companies, thus seeking to consolidate new forms of business, as highlighted by Al Shaar and al. (2015).

The concept of "human-centered renewal" explores the influence of technology on the "people" element within the context of the MIT model. This orientation, focused on behavioral change, emphasized empowerment, emphasizing the need to delegate responsibility and power to employees. The emphasis on cross-functional training for managers, users, and IT professionals aims to build consensus and acquire the skills necessary to achieve internal synergy (Leclercq, 2007). It assesses this issue from individual, executive, organizational, and societal perspectives, emphasizing the importance of linking structure and strategy to people to achieve the expected productivity and profitability through information technology. This orientation takes an interpretive approach to examining the impact of information technology on the human experience, advocating a decentralization of power structures, a dispersion of knowledge and responsibilities throughout the organization, and the empowerment of employees at all levels. Thus, the balance between technology, organization and human actors becomes a crucial source of success in implementing IT-based strategic change (Moh'd Al-adaileh, 2009).

Figure 1: MIT Model (Morton, 1991)

2. Strategic Alignment Model

In response to the growing recognition of the strategic role of information systems within organizations, Henderson and Venkatraman (1989) developed a conceptual framework for defining the strategic use of information technology, known as the Strategic Alignment Model (SAM). Their work on alignment has been presented through several iterations (Henderson and al., 1992; Venkatraman and al., 1993; Henderson and Venkatraman, 1999). These different versions fundamentally share the same basic model, with minor adjustments to the theoretical content. This evolution suggests a constant desire to refine and adapt the model to

better address the nuances of the ever-changing strategic and technological landscape.

The Strategic Alignment Model (SAM) explains IT alignment through two management components: strategic fit and functional integration. Strategic fit measures the extent to which the firm's internal structures align with its strategic position, highlighting the importance of the administrative structure in supporting the organization's position in its competitive market. In parallel, functional integration assesses the fit between the business and IT functional areas. Henderson and Venkatraman (1999) identify four internal functional areas, also referred to as "alignment factors": business strategy, IT strategy, organizational infrastructure and processes, and IT infrastructure and processes. The central objective of the strategic alignment model is to ensure a harmonious fit between these functional areas, where true alignment occurs when all areas simultaneously achieve an appropriate state of uniformity. This approach emphasizes the need for simultaneous and concurrent attention to all four areas to achieve full strategic alignment (Smaczny 2001).

Since its initial introduction, the Strategic Alignment Model (SAM) has played a central role as the foundation for much research on information systems alignment. Various studies have specifically focused on the alignment of strategic and structural elements, both on the business and IT sides, or on specific pairs of these elements (Palmer and Markus, 2000). In addition, the impact of this alignment on organizational performance has also been carefully examined. The emphasis on the simultaneous and concordant consideration of all four domains, as well as the multitude of research adopting a cross-disciplinary approach, has led some researchers to consider IS alignment as a form of "synchronization." According to this perspective, any change in one alignment factor is seen as inducing changes in each of the other factors (Sabherwal and Jeyaraj, 2015).

The Strategic Alignment Model (SAM) is based on the implicit assumption that organizational performance is closely linked to proper alignment of the four key factors. This underlying idea suggests that when these factors are optimally aligned, overall firm performance is efficient. Conversely, it suggests that firms exhibiting high performance have likely achieved a minimum level of alignment. When one alignment factor changes, the model implies that adjustments must occur in each of the other factors to maintain overall harmony. Thus, the SAM represents a delicate state of equilibrium where any change in one factor requires coordinated adaptations in the others, highlighting the need for constant alignment to preserve system effectiveness (Chan, 2008).

Henderson and Venkatraman (1999) expand on the model by introducing a clear distinction with the definition of four types of inter-domain alignments, which he refers to as "coalignment." These specific categories propose a holistic and dynamic approach to effectively integrate information

and communication technologies (ICT) throughout an organization. First, strategic coalignment, called "strategic fit," represents the traditional alignment based on a hierarchical relationship between the external entity and the internal entity. This stems from strategic management where business strategy exerts a significant influence on the technical infrastructure and organizational processes. The second coalignment emphasizes the impact of ICT by identifying the best technologies for product/market positioning. This approach highlights the necessary adjustments at both the technical infrastructure and process levels, which can materialize through technological alliances between companies. The third coalignment focuses on the choice of ICT to stimulate new products and services, which can, in turn, influence the overall strategy of the company. This coalignment helps develop a competitive advantage by capitalizing on the opportunities offered by ICT. Finally, the fourth coalignment addresses the adaptation of ICT by highlighting the internal repercussions of an ICT strategy. It highlights the necessary adjustments in technical infrastructures and internal processes, thus contributing to the overall improvement of service quality within the organization. Together, these coalignments constitute a comprehensive framework for the strategic management of ICT, enabling smooth integration and optimization of the benefits they can offer to the entire company (Chan and Reich, 2007).

Figure 2: SAM model (Henderson and Venkatraman, 1989)

VI. CONCLUSION

The Following this literature review, it appears that information systems cannot be reduced to their technical or instrumental dimensions alone. They are emerging as complex socio-technical objects, simultaneously driving operational efficiency and driving organizational change. Their ability to structure collective action, transform coordination methods, and support corporate strategy makes them a central element of contemporary managerial dynamics. Information systems thus lie at the intersection of human, technological, strategic, and political logics, which explains the diversity of theoretical frameworks used to understand them, ranging from adoption theory to the

sociology of appropriation, including strategic alignment approaches.

The historical and conceptual evolution of the field reveals a clear shift: initially focused on the technologies themselves, IS research has gradually shifted toward more integrative approaches, examining the social, cultural, and political conditions of their deployment. Models such as the Strategic Alignment Model (SAM) and the Management of Information Technology (MIT) now offer robust analytical frameworks for understanding the contribution of information systems to organizational performance. However, these models, while useful, would benefit from being better aligned with concrete usage contexts, the actual practices of stakeholders, and the evolutionary trajectories of technologies within organizations.

This research also highlights certain persistent limitations in the literature. On the one hand, conceptual fragmentation persists, with each theoretical school tending to mobilize its own categories of analysis without always seeking bridges with other perspectives. On the other hand, empirical work often remains confined to short timescales and specific contexts, limiting its explanatory scope and transferability. In this context, the development of integrative approaches capable of crossing the micro (uses and practices), meso (organizational structures and processes), and macro (strategies and institutions) levels appears to be a promising avenue. Methodological hybridization, combining longitudinal case studies, action research designs, and mixed methods, also represents a relevant lever for renewing the analysis of information systems in management science.

This theoretical article thus aims to contribute to the structuring of the field of information systems research in management science. By reexamining disciplinary anchors, epistemological positions, and managerial issues related to information systems, it opens up perspectives for future research that is more integrated, better contextualized, and resolutely focused on understanding the dynamics of organizational transformation. These future investigations should pay particular attention to how information systems are concretely reconfiguring management practices, value chains, control mechanisms, as well as power and legitimization relationships within contemporary organizations.

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